

Influence of the Ediacaran–Cambrian record on the Late Paleozoic tectonics of the Central Iberian Zone

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The lithological composition controls the rheology of rock ensembles under stress. Rock deformation, including the geometry of resulting structures, differs according to the physical properties of the objects to be deformed and deformation conditions. In this way, the type of protolith (sedimentary or igneous) and the thermal conditions of deformation are a key factors that can control how and where the lithosphere is deformed. In this work, we present a case example about how the contrasted lithological composition of different sections of a lithosphere may have controlled the structures created during orogenesis. We use a case example from the Central Iberian Zone of the Iberian Massif (Hiendelaencina, Spain), which contains a lithological record related to the dynamics of a peri-Gondwanan arc system that spans from the Neoproterozoic to the Cambrian, and a different record related to the onset of extensional tectonics and the establishment of a passive margin from the Ordovician through to the Devonian (e.g. Fuenlabrada et al. 2016).

In the Hiendelaencina region, the oldest series (micaschists, quartzites and metasediments) represents the deposit of pelites and sandstones in a terrigenous continental shelf environment during the Neoproterozoic and Cambrian (Angón and Cardeñosa formations), probably under the influence of the tectonic activity of a Cadomian arc-system (Villaseca et al. 2014). This series was followed by the deposit of pelites and sandstones in a margin that underwent extensional tectonic activity during the Ordovician (Constante, Alto Rey and Rodada formations). That tectonic activity has been related to the dynamics of a peri-Gondwanan arc, and is closely linked to widespread magmatism (García-Arias et al. 2018). In the study area, magmas generated in this context intruded the existing series, giving rise to granitic massifs and volcano-sedimentary series. Those protoliths can be currently observed as a variety of orthogneisses, including the felsic augen orthogneiss of the Antoñita Fm. (after an Ordovician aplopegmatitic “S” type granitoid; Navidad 1978, Fernández Rodríguez 1991, Talavera, 2009), and the Cambrian-Ordovician, fine- and coarse-grained augen gneisses of the Hiendelaencina Fm., which are equivalent to the “Ollo de Sapo” Fm. (García-Arias et al. 2018). The regional distribution of the metagranitoids is not random, as they occur mostly within the Ediacaran and Cambrian series. The lack of such igneous massifs in most of the older-than-Cambrian series of the region defines a two-layer pre-Variscan structure: a lower layer made up of granitoids and volumetrically minor sedimentary rocks, and an upper layer made up of sedimentary rocks.

The Variscan Orogeny took place during the Late Paleozoic as a consequence of the continental collision between Gondwana, Laurussia and other peri-continental terranes (Díez Fernández et al. 2016). The metamorphic basement of the Hiendelaencina sector has been affected by three Variscan deformation phases, which collectively contributed to the recrystallization of the pre-Variscan protoliths of the region as to be the ensemble of metamorphic rocks we see today (354–295 Ma; González Lodeiro 1980, Fernández Rodríguez 1991, Rubio Pascual et al. 2013). The first phase of deformation generated E-verging, overturned folds and an axial plane foliation. The second phase of deformation generated a top-to-the-SE ductile, extensional shear zone, which overprinted the former structural and metamorphic record. Overprinting was heterogeneous in the upper block and within the shear zone, but much more intense in the latter, where former foliations were fully

or mostly reworked. The third phase of deformation generated upright folds and an associated strike-slip shear zone.

Structural and metamorphic data indicates that the upper limit of the extensional shear zone generated during the second phase of Variscan deformation is located atop the upper boundary of the lithostratigraphic series that included the Cambrian and Ordovician igneous massifs. This match suggests us that the contrasted rheology between the two layers described before, played an important role in controlling the boundaries of the shear zone, which exploited the rheologically weak nature of such boundary to accommodate extensional tectonic flow. This shear zone, despite being related to the extensional collapse of the Variscan Orogen, does not seem to have subtracted or attenuated much of the orogenic crust upwards beyond that rheological boundary, so the latter could have conditioned how Variscan extensional flow was accommodated. Many extensional domes related to the collapse of the Variscan orogen are cored by sequences that include abundant Cambrian-Ordovician orthogneisses and are surrounded by series that occupy the hanging wall of extensional structures and are significantly poorer in metaigneous rocks by comparison than the dome cores. The two-layer rheological structure is an inheritance from the Ediacaran to Early Paleozoic tectonics of the peri-Gondwanan domain, and may have conditioned the patterns of Variscan orogenic collapse.

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